

Raw aesthetics.

Rhythm and entrainment in the aesthetic component of experience.

Carlos Vara Sánchez
Ca' Foscari University *

Abstract

On many occasions we are unwittingly constrained by aesthetic circumstances. Not only in those rare instances in which we have so-called aesthetic experiences, but much more frequently in ordinary but potentially relevant aspects of everyday life. Any aesthetic theory committed to this idea should be able to establish a continuity between both types of experience. To fulfill this aim, in this paper I propose an enactive model of an aesthetic component of experience based on a notion of rhythm as open entrainment that follows John Dewey's aesthetic theory and recent research on aesthetics and dynamic aspects of cognition from the perspective both of philosophy and of the neurosciences. I will define some critical points of this aesthetic component: an unrealized impulsion able to trigger an aesthetic asymmetry, an aesthetic affordance, and an oscillatory regime of aesthetic metastability. I suggest that these raw elements present differential dynamics regarding the mobilization of narrative and attentional resources and that these two cognitive aspects, reciprocally coupled with bodily and environmental oscillations, enact a cognitive rhythm that shapes the interaction that give rise to it through entrainment.

Keywords:

Rhythm, Dewey, aesthetics, enactivism, entrainment, experience

1 Introduction

How does the aesthetic work in experience? John Dewey argued that “[i]n order to *understand* the esthetic in its ultimate and approved forms, one must begin with it in the raw; in the events and scenes that hold the attentive eye and ear of a man, arousing his interests and affording him enjoyment as he looks and listens” (Dewey 1980: 3). This continuity of the aesthetic was already hinted at by William James: “The two great aesthetic principles of richness and ease, dominate our intellectual as well as our sensuous life” (James 1983: 943). More recently, Mark Johnson has contended: “All experience is shaped by its aesthetic dimensions [...] Aesthetic, then, pertains not just to art, beauty, and so-called aesthetic experience and judgment, but also to all the pervasive structures and processes by which we humans experience and make meaning, such as images, image schemas, qualities, emotions, and feelings” (Johnson 2017: 227).

In this paper, I will not dwell on the nature of aesthetic experiences. I will not try to make a case either for their distinct existence or against it. Rather, I will argue that we experience objects and events aesthetically owing to a set of cognitive processes and their interactions that is referred to as the aesthetic component of experience (ACE). That is, the ACE is not the contents of experience, but the dynamic form – i.e., the rhythm – that shapes the ongoing interaction of different cognitive processes that give rise to it. This paper is framed within the non-representational tenets shared by enactivists and ecological psychologists. Yet, my emphasis on the cognitive role of emerging interactions between oscillatory components at the intersection of body, brain, and environment definitively places me within the enactivist camp. For that reason, I believe that the model I present in this paper might be helpful in developing an enactive approach to aesthetics that goes beyond paradigmatic and controversial aesthetic experiences by presenting a continuous component rooted in pre-reflective processes, while also entering into a fruitful dialogue with ecological approaches such as Vicente

* This result is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement n. 794484.
The paper reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Raja (2018, 2019, 2020)'s theory of resonance as a foundation for radical embodiment, and enactive conceptualizations of attunement (Colombetti 2013; Ryan, Gallagher in press).

My model builds upon a concept of rhythm as “an evolving pattern of oscillations able to entrain other oscillations” (Author 2020) based on Dewey’s aesthetic philosophy, which continues to be one of the most comprehensive theories about aesthetics, and which has recently undergone somewhat of a resurgence thanks to his being acknowledged as a forerunner of enactive approaches to cognition. That is, the ACE will be regarded as a rhythm enacted by different nested oscillators from the body, brain, and environment that presents reflective aspects (aesthetic metastability) and pre-reflective aspects (cognitive asymmetry and unrealized entrainment) separated by a dynamic attentional threshold that can be overcome by accepting the invitation of an aesthetic affordance. Depending on which of these processes are active at a given time, an experience¹ driven by the ACE could be so weak as to be deemed irrelevant, affecting our decisions without us being aware of it, or be able to reach an overt level at which we feel the whole experience as aesthetic. In this paper, I present an enactive theoretical model – open to empirical verification or falsification – that will also take into account recent research in other philosophical traditions, cognitive neuroscience, and dynamic systems theory. This model aims to follow Luiz Pessoa’s desideratum for future research on cognition: “[A] framework based on processes that are inherently formulated in terms of interactions and how they evolve temporally” (Pessoa 2017: 13). That is, I do not intend to present an exhaustive list of elements that play a role in the ACE; rather, I will highlight some dynamically relevant nodes able to shunt general experience toward the aesthetic.

To this end, in section 2, I begin by considering different understandings of the notion of experience within an aesthetic context. Then, in section 2.1, I present John Dewey’s aesthetic thinking and my enactive notion of rhythm based in entrainment. In section 3, I propose the different aspects of the model of the ACE. Finally, in section 4, I address some open issues for future research regarding the role of rhythm in embodied cognition.

2 Aesthetics: experience and rhythms

The concept of aesthetic experience seems to have become increasingly controversial in the last few decades. There are those who consider the aesthetic experience to be a successor of the experience of beauty that is caused by attending to the formal and/or aesthetic and/or expressive properties of a work of art (Carroll 2012: 173). This and other similar definitions have been deemed ‘narrow’ conceptions of the aesthetic experience. Broader characterizations consider it as “sensuous perception, informed by cognition, enlarged by imagination, and prompting emotional responses” (Goldman 2013: 323). However, others declare themselves skeptical even about the usefulness of the term, contending that “we tend to call any strong (or intense, or emotionally significant) experience that we have in an aesthetic context ‘aesthetic experience’. But this can mean very different things” (Nanay 2016: 12). In a similar vein, Marie Brincker (2015: 130) hypothesizes: “[A]esthetic experiences are indeed a special subset of perceptual experiences, but distinguished through these relative dynamic relations rather than object features and attitudes alone”. As a consequence, she contends: “[I]t cannot be stressed enough that under a process-oriented framework aesthetic experiences need not be ‘all-or-none’. Rather, an analysis of the aspects contributing to specific experiences could be used to elucidate rather than eradicate borderline cases and their respective temporal and contextual structures” (Brincker 2015: 132). An apparently similar

¹ Even though this paper orbits around John Dewey’s aesthetic philosophy, my use of the concept of experience differs from his. Dewey considered experience to be the whole set of interactions and events resulting from the engagement between an organism and the environment (1980, p. 22). However, as Roberta Dreon (2019) neatly explains: “Dewey would not have accepted the maximum extension of the notion of cognition, namely the enactivist thesis that all living systems are cognitive systems” (p.4). Dewey considered cognition just a phase or an aspect of experience (Dewey 1980, p. 28). Thus, while I understand cognition from an enactivist point of view, my concept of experience is the common one: I take it to mean the events and instances of interactions that leave an impression on us.

argument is that of Alva Noë, who, instead of aesthetic experience, favors the use of concepts such as ‘aesthetic sense’ and ‘aesthetic responses’, which he considers to be “not symptoms or reactions or stable qualities. They are actions. They are modes of participation. They are more moments of conversation” (Noë 2015: 132-133). This argument fits nicely within the general framework on his sensorimotor enactive theory; however, as has already been pointed out (Forlè 2018), Noë has not developed the dynamics underlying these engagements. On the radical side of the enactive approach, Daniel Hutto suggests a “de-intellectualized characterization of mind that rethinks basic mentality, uncompromisingly, in terms of extended interactions with an environment. On such an account, engaged interactions of the right kind – but nothing short of them – would suffice for the occurrence of the relevant aesthetic phenomena” (Hutto 2015: 226). In the field of empirical aesthetics some scholars (Skov and Nadal 2020) have recently noted the absence of current evidence supporting aesthetic experiences as a particular kind of experience, different from ordinary hedonic appreciations. This rebuttal of the specificity of aesthetic experience reinforces Dewey’s aesthetic aim: “[T]o restore continuity between the refined and intensified forms of experience that are works of art and the everyday events, doings, and sufferings that are universally recognized to constitute experience” (Dewey 1980: 2). In order to do so, we have to steer toward “the ordinary forces and conditions of experience that we do not usually regard as esthetic” (Dewey 1980: 2). That is, we must widen our focus from aesthetic experiences to the aesthetic in experience.

One might claim that the biggest issue we face with the term ‘aesthetic experience’ is the implicit assumption that the ‘aesthetic’ is one specific type of experience detached from other non-aesthetic experiences. This idea points to a modularity of experience that goes against current ideas in cognitive science that emphasize the importance of global dynamics and interactions (Pessoa 2017). However, should we decide to renounce the concept of aesthetic experience, we will still have instances of experience capable of offering “affordances that short-circuit in a way that comes back to the perceiving agent, disrupting ordinary engagements, and creating possibilities that are not realizable in current or established frameworks” (Gallagher 2011: 113). This and other similar characterizations of aesthetic engagements refer to particularly rewarding and potentially life-enriching heterogeneous experiences; however, are we to believe that these experiences are instantaneous all-or-nothing events with shallow cognitive roots? This hardly seems reconcilable with an enactive view of cognition and with our own personal experiences². These episodes mostly take time to develop and they are not under complete voluntary control³.

For the purpose of throwing light on the dynamics of these engagements, I will draw on Dewey’s ideas on rhythm and aesthetics.

2.1 Aesthetic rhythms

Dewey grounds rhythms in nature. Rhythms are not metaphorical concepts, but dynamic rearrangements of energies that tie together the environment and some phenomena that takes place within it. According to Dewey, some of

²Elsewhere (Author 2020) I have illustrated some necessary but not sufficient rhythmic features of a particular case of paradigmatic aesthetic experience that I have called the ‘artistic way of experiencing’: Awareness of the experience mediated by an element from the environment, a positive feedback dynamic, the alteration of the sense of agency, and experiential coherence (Author 2020: 92-93). These aspects are specific experiential contents constrained by reflective rhythmicity. In the present paper, I will instead focus on the dynamics and interactions of the whole rhythm of the aesthetic component of experience.

³Bence Nanay (2016) nicely summarizes this point: “We stand in front of it and we fail to experience it in an aesthetic manner, in spite of the fact that we really want to. Maybe we are too fixated on the lecture we need to give in half an hour. Or maybe we are still thinking of the conversation we had over lunch with a friend. Or maybe we are just too sleepy. In any case, the aesthetic experience is not forthcoming. In this respect, aesthetic experiences are very different from the ordinary perceptual experiences of, say, color or shape. If I am looking at an object and want to see its color, this will guarantee, barring some odd circumstances, that I experience its color. This is apparently not so when it comes to aesthetic experiences” (pp. 16-17).

these natural rhythms include ponds moving in ripples, the waving of branches in the wind, or the beating of a bird's wing. (Dewey 1980: 161). We have always partaken of this rhythmic fabric, for – in what could be considered a proto-enactivist statement – Dewey affirms that “life goes on in an environment; not merely *in* it but because of it, through interaction with it” (Dewey 1980: 12). However, not all rhythms are equal. There is a particular rhythm that, if present in experience, makes this experience *an* experience: doing and undergoing in relationship (Dewey 1980: 46). This rhythmic relationship is what makes possible for an experience to be at the same time a summing up and fulfillment of what precedes, carrying expectations tensely forward (Dewey 1980: 179). That is, for Dewey rhythm is not something superimposed upon an element but the operation through which material effects its own culmination in experience (1980: 153). Rhythms are emergent formal properties of certain interactions. And, when the particular rhythmic form of ‘doing and undergoing in relationship’ is perceived, it becomes an aesthetic rhythm and the experience aesthetic (Dewey 1980: 169). Every experience thus can present an aesthetic quality, and although this does not mean that every experience is an aesthetic experience, according to Dewey, there is no clear-cut differentiation but continuity between the aesthetic in experience and aesthetic experiences. In fact, it could be argued that, for Dewey, rhythm – understood as a dynamic rearrangement of energies – is a potential feature of natural phenomena and the particular rhythm of doing and undergoing in relationship is a necessary but not sufficient condition of an aesthetic quality of experience that, when it enters perception, becomes an aesthetic experience.

Dewey's understanding of rhythm clearly differs from the prevailing one nowadays, which stems from Plato's *Laws*, which define rhythm as “order in movement” (665a). Dewey, by contrast, is adamant in not identifying rhythm with literal recurrence (what he calls the tick-tock theory), arguing that rhythm is “ordered variation of changes. When there is a uniformly even flow, with no variations of intensity or speed, there is no rhythm” (Dewey 1980: 160). Dewey's concept shows his interest in dynamic processes as opposed to stable abstraction. He thinks of rhythm as something that is in virtue of what it *does*. And what rhythm does is to reorganize energies, connect entities, and affect them in harmonic yet not always predictable ways. However, despite Dewey's emphasis on rhythm as a connecting form, he focuses almost exclusively on the temporal aspect, and not so much on how different rhythms combine and affect one another.

At this point, the concept of entrainment fits perfectly. Entrainment can be defined as the tendency of two or more oscillators to align their frequencies (Pikovsky, Rosenblum, Kurths 2001). Entrainment has been ubiquitously found in both physical and biological systems, including human beings. Researchers speak of perceptual, autonomic, physiological, motor and social types of entrainment in human cognition (Trost and Vuilleumier 2013). The mechanisms behind every manifestation of entrainment, as well the ways they affect one another are still open to discussion and are an object of research; however, it has been proposed that we consider them to be components of the same phenomenon (Trost, Labbé and Grandjean 2017: 105). From my point of view, when Dewey contends that “[e]ven the tick-tock of the clock as it is heard varies, because what is *heard* is an interaction of the physical event with changing pulsations of organic response” (Dewey 1980: 174), it can be considered an example of entrainment. He refers to how our experience is rhythmized to the form of the interaction between two oscillators – in this case, the fixed one of the clock and the entrained one of the ‘organic response’. There is ample literature (see Lakatos, Gross & Thut 2019 for a comprehensive review) on ‘neuronal entrainment’ –i.e., the coupling of rhythmic brain activity to external and internal rhythmic events. Nonetheless, if we add the well-documented capacity of voluntary bodily rhythms such as respiration (Zelano et al. 2016) and involuntary ones such as heart rate oscillations (Mather and Thayer 2018) to entrain different forms of brain oscillatory activity, entrainment emerges as a phenomenon that addresses oscillatory interactions at the intersection between the brain, body, and environment. These results seem consistent with the framework of coordination dynamics (Kelso 1995; Kelso and Tognoli 2007), which frames the neural system as composed by non-linearly coupled non-linear oscillations.

Elsewhere, I have presented a definition of rhythm as “an evolving pattern of oscillations able to entrain other oscillations” (Author 2020). This conceptualization does not ignore the temporal aspect of rhythms – it is present in the

word ‘evolving’ – but makes continuity and pervasiveness their main features. This extremely relational definition considers rhythms as particular patterns that emerge from the interaction of two or more oscillatory elements. Speaking of human beings, we can focus on the emergent rhythm of the contraction of the heart – caused by the interaction of electric impulses generated by cells of the sinoatrial node – but this rhythm can also be regarded as part of a bigger rhythm, along with other mechanical rhythms related to respiration and gastric activity that are reciprocally regulated. And the resultant bodily rhythm can be considered an element that makes part of a much more complex rhythm, together with brain and environmental oscillations, all of which enact nested dynamic constraints⁴ that affect the whole through entrainment and have an effect on experience. Yet, this does not mean that a unitary, constant oscillation along the body and the brain could be registered. It means that different oscillations are nested in such a way that variations in one of these local rhythms affect the whole rhythmicity. The different oscillations that we find in the body, brain, and environment not only serve their specific function, but contribute to the enactment of an ongoing set of rhythmic constraints constitutive of cognition necessary for the modulation and attunement of the whole rhythm. This is not a fixed property, but, as Dewey says, a form that emerges from the interaction of some raw materials (Dewey 1980: 152).

Coming back to aesthetics, I follow Dewey’s account of an aesthetic rhythm as a particular form of experience. Nonetheless, where Dewey characterizes this rhythm as a perceived relationship between doing and undergoing, I will provide in the next section a model of the ACE mainly based on the interaction of narrative and attentional cognitive processes enacted by the confluence of brain, body, and environment oscillations able to constrain different pre-reflective and reflective aspects of experience in relevant timescales⁵. I will contend that the ACE does not always go beyond the pre-reflective but, when it does reach the reflective side of experience, this aspect will be constrained by the ongoing pre-reflective process. In other words, the most common impact of the ACE is on ordinary, non-glamorous, but relevant, aspects of everyday life – e.g., the influence of the external aspect of a product in consumers’ price sensitivity (Mumcu and Kimzan 2015) and product evaluation (Hoegg, Alba, and Dahl 2010), the unrealized influence of the pitch of the candidates’ voices on voters (Klofstad, Anderson, Nowicki 2015). Another divergence between Dewey’s theory and the model I propose concerns his emphasis on the aesthetic as a set of connected but successive phases leading to a consummation. He argues that the anticipation of this consummation is what makes an experience aesthetic (1980: 57). In this regard, I will focus mainly on the ACE as a set of nested oscillatory processes whose effects accumulate throughout the whole experience in narratively relevant timescales while constraining potential outcomes of sensorimotor nature.

My main point is that the aesthetic component is not triggered by a specific *what*, but is a particular *how*. I do not restrict the aesthetic component to particular events or objects, such as artworks, but to specific engagements between human beings and the environment. Hence, aesthetics becomes a way to address, explore, and understand how certain interactions take place, their roots, dynamics, and potential outcomes. For example, this aesthetic component can be useful in an educational context to try to enhance attentional and memory processes by controlling environmental circumstances such as light conditions, background music, and the affordances of educational tools. On a not-so-positive note, the aesthetic is constantly used as a backdoor to manipulate us into certain actions – is there any more obvious aesthetic hook than the jingling and blinking of a slot machine? In sum, this focus on the ACE aims to underline the continuity and dynamics of the aesthetic not only in the exceptional circumstances of museums, concert halls and forests, but in our daily life activities connected with education, shopping, and intersubjective relations.

⁴I share the definition of constraints offered by Alicia Juarrero (2015), who defines them as “any event, mechanism, or condition that alters a system’s probability space” (514). This conceptualization makes room for the possibility of enabling constraints, those that expand a system’s probability space.

⁵Francisco Varela (1999) distinguished three relevant timescales of intrinsic temporality: (1) elementary timescale (up to 100 milliseconds), (2) integrative scale (up to few seconds), and (3) narrative timescale (durations above few seconds).

3 A dynamic model of the aesthetic component of experience

The model (fig. 1) I introduce in this section addresses rhythmic interactions of sensorimotor, affective, and other cognitive forms originating in a system composed by brain, body, and environment. Although there is the unresolved question of the correlation between these underlying cognitive oscillatory patterns and the rhythmic relation of the contents of experience, this is a discussion that clearly exceeds the scope of the present paper. For the moment, it is sufficient to say that I am sympathetic to the idea of temporospatial dynamics as the ‘common currency’ behind the mind-brain relationship (Northoff, Wainio-Theberge, and Evers 2019). In the context of the current paper, this amounts to holding that the ACE can be characterized by changes in cognitive oscillatory patterns and that these in turn produce qualitative changes in experience.

Fig. 1 Schema of the ACE. At the pre-reflective side of the ACE (P-R), the initial unrealized impulsion (I) triggers an aesthetic asymmetry (II) in which faster sensorimotor attentional (A) aspects and slower narrative (N) resources regulate each other. This asymmetry is subject to environmental oscillations (E. O.) and bodily oscillations (B. O.) entrains experience and our sensorimotor engagement with the world. If there is sustained priming, the attentional threshold (III) will be reached and an aesthetic affordance will be perceived. Accepting this affordance means entering the reflective side of the ACE (R), which presents a fluctuation between narrative (N) and attentional (A) brain networks in a regime of aesthetic metastability (IV) which also entrains experience and our sensorimotor engagement with the world and is subject to influence from bodily and environmental oscillations. All the different oscillatory components enact the general rhythmicity of the ACE (vertical wave).

3.1 The aesthetic affordance at the attentional threshold

Bence Nanay contends that in some paradigmatic cases of aesthetic experience “attention is distributed with regards to properties but focused with regards to object” (Nanay 2016: 23). That is, from a psychological point of view, our attention happens to wander around certain features of a single entity. However, he repeatedly makes it clear that this ‘aesthetic attention’ is neither necessary nor sufficient for all types of aesthetic experiences (Nanay 2016: 28). Instead, what he regards as a “crucial (and maybe even close to universal) feature of aesthetic experience” is “attending to the relation between the perceived object and the quality of the experience of this object” (Nanay 2019: 39-40). However, there is the question of how a cognitive rhythm is able to connect object and agent enacted, and how it entrains other cognitive aspects and constrain our experience. Nanay (2019) concedes that there is no easy answer: he merely says that softening the focus of our attention is not under voluntary control and that it takes time (p. 37). I agree with Nanay that an attentional shift is an important feature of the reflective aspect of aesthetically relevant experiences. Nonetheless, I think that attention is not enough. Attention has to be drawn to something narratively relevant and we have to actively engage with this narratively relevant aspect that has come to our attention. The aesthetic appears in experience as the consequence of a cognitive ‘one-two’ by attentional and narrative aspects of cognition solicited by an aesthetic affordance that appears at an attentional threshold.

In the ACE model, the attentional threshold marks the moment we experience a match between what we perceive and a previously concealed activity originating in the cognitive background leading to the emergence of an aesthetic affordance. That is, an event or object will enter reflective experience as it entrains our attention and will invite to a particular type of action. This aesthetic threshold is not a fixed point; rather, its relative position – i.e., how salient an inner state or an element from the environment has to be to draw our attention – will depend on the interaction between cognitive processes and the environment. In a metaphorical sense, this threshold will be lower when a slight activity in the cognitive background suffices to generate reflective activity associated with the ACE. This may be the case when we put ourselves in a favorable condition by previously exposing ourselves to related experiences or by eliminating potential distractions to our exploratory attention. On the other hand, the threshold at which the affordance appears will be higher and will require more salient stimuli if we are lost in our thoughts, engaged in another activity, or constrained by more pressing needs.

Brincker has recently introduced a remarkable framework for aesthetic perception from an embodied and dynamic point of view. One key concept is that of aesthetic affordance: “[A]n affordance of perceptual engagement but yet non-action, which opens up possibilities for using our minds – and brains – in ways we do not in our regular practically engaged modes of perception” (Brincker 2015: 123). These ‘un-actable’ affordances preclude a goal-oriented reaction, opening us “to an otherwise difficult intimacy with the perceptual experience and virtual other” (p. 125). This idea resonates with Shaun Gallagher’s characterization of the perception of art as involving non-realizable, non-practical, and non-interactionable affordances able to come back and make the one having the experience aware of his possibilities, by disrupting ordinary engagements (Gallagher 2011: 109). These two scholars’ emphasis on action-related aspects sets them apart from Martin Krampen, who – to the best of my knowledge – coined the notion of aesthetic affordance to speak of out-of-joint experiences caused by the vastness of certain aesthetic scenes and the limits of our body (Krampen 1991).

I am not interested in the discussion whether the above-mentioned scholars stretch Gibson’s classical concept of affordance beyond a reasonable point, for I consider aesthetic affordances to be our best option to tackle the experience opened at the attentional threshold by the rhythmic cognitive constraints of the ACE, in line with recent research that, combining phenomenological, dynamical, and non-representational approaches, has characterized affordances as having effects on cognition, behavior, and social and cultural niches (Withagen et al. 2012; Bruineberg & Rietveld 2014; Rietveld & Kiverstein 2014; Ramstead et al. 2016; Dings 2018; Dings 2019). However, I do not share Brincker’s assumption that

what makes aesthetic affordances invite a different kind of engagement is the fact that most artistic media offer asymmetric, non-interactive modes of perception that block our capacity to act upon the perceived affordance (Brinker 2015: 123-124). Nor do I share Brincker's Kantian tendency to oppose a goal-directed attitude and an aesthetic one and her emphasis on non-goal-directedness as a necessary condition for freedom of the imagination (Brincker 2015: 120). I contend that, in the case of aesthetic affordances, perceiving them is almost tantamount to accepting their invitation. But this does not mean the absence of action; rather, the action we are invited to, at least in its initial stages, is almost irresistible and this is due to the fact that aesthetic affordances mainly solicit through their mineness.

Roy Dings (2018) affirms the importance of three aspects for the dynamic process implied in whether affordances solicit an action or not: valence, force, and mineness. Mineness is the "extent to which an affordance is experienced as being close to 'who I am' or, more precisely, 'who I take myself to be'. That is, mineness emerges from the activity of the "background of earlier and co-temporal experiences, thoughts, memories, proprioceptions, interoceptions, etc." (Slors and Jongepier 2014: 201) that constitute the narrative self. This mineness of an affordance will be salient if there are no pressing needs constraining our field of affordances – i.e. "The affordances that stand out as relevant for a particular individual in a particular situation" (Bruineberg and Rietveld 2014: 2). This is not to say that in order for us to perceive aesthetic affordances as inviting we have to show disinterest toward the world; rather, aesthetic affordances will be mostly at hand when we are left to wonder and wander: it will be more likely for us to perceive the aesthetic affordances of a pond if we are neither thirsty, nor tired, nor lost. According to Dings, biographical or evocative objects are able to exert different narrative functions: expressing, stabilizing, motivating, triggering particular memories, and serving as a soundboard for meaning-making (Dings 2019: 15-16). However, I believe that the common denominator of aesthetic affordances is their inviting to a narratively relevant experience that resonates with the mineness of the affordance. They do not need to entice us with a life-changing experience. The strength of its mineness will reside in its univocity: an object has to be experienced as *the* object to affect an element of this narrative self. Yet, for an aesthetic affordance to emerge, our attention will have to cover relevant features of the environmental element and narrative aspects supporting this relevance. More specifically, for an object or event to invite through an aesthetic affordance it will have to be attentionally relevant and present a narratively relevant level of mineness –e.g., we realize that we are thinking of how a particular object affects us, or we become aware of how sitting at a particular place in the bar makes us feel at home. That is, aesthetic affordances are more or less overt opportunities to modulate, soothe, enhance, rewrite, explore, feel, forget or merely reflect upon aspects of the narrative self, such as memories, interests, likings, desires or habits in a socially situated, extended, intersubjective, and embodied context. Accepting the invitation to an action brought by an aesthetic affordance leads to an experience constrained by attentionally relevant processes of the narrative self.

3.2 Aesthetic metastability

Low frequency brain rhythms are known to be entrained by sensorimotor events, cognitive processes such as decision making, memory or motivation and interoceptive processes (Lakatos, Gross & Thut 2019) while being able to entrain high frequency oscillations thanks to cross-frequency mechanisms⁶. That is, they are at the crossroads between bodily, environmental, and faster brain oscillations. Among these rhythms, the dynamics of activation and deactivation of brain networks (also known as neural networks) are in the range of 0.01-0.1 Hz (Vanhaudenhuyse et al. 2011), which fits Varela

⁶Brain and bodily oscillations are not isolated, rather, they interact and modulate each other through a set of processes known as cross-frequency coupling, such as phase-amplitude coupling and phase-phase coupling. Phase-amplitude coupling is one organizational law observed in the interaction between two or more waves in which the phase of the lower frequency ones modifies the amplitude of those of higher frequency. On the other hand, phase-phase coupling is the amplitude independent locking of an amount of cycles of the higher frequency oscillation and an amount of cycles of the lower frequency oscillation. This mechanism is deemed to play a significant role in neuronal communication (Fries 2005)

(1999)'s narrative timescale. Yet, the precise number, functions, and borders of each network are subject to debate, owing to potential extensive overlapping between them. Overlapping, in return, seems to provide flexibility to adapt to different tasks and situations (Najafi et al. 2016). Taken together, these circumstances point to brain networks being relevant rhythmic constraints of cognition and experience.

When considering the different brain networks, the Default Mode Network (DMN) seems an obvious candidate to play a role in this narratively relevant rhythmicity and even in paradigmatic aesthetic experiences⁷. Recent data indicates that, among other functions, the DMN supports emotional processing, self-referential mental activity, and the recollection of prior experiences (see Raichle 2015 for a review). Although the mechanisms of the activation and deactivation of the different hubs that compose it are not completely known, research (Smith, Mitchell, and Duncan 2018; Kang, Pae, and Park 2019) suggests that this network mediates transitions between cognitive states – i.e., by switching from a state like perceiving to desiring, from knowing to feeling, etc. However, cognitive networks do not work in isolation: they overlap anatomically and integrate functionally. Regarding DMN, there is a remarkable degree of periodical anticorrelation with a network linked to external awareness: the dorsal attentional network (Fox et al. 2005). That is, while performing certain tasks, the dominance between the two networks fluctuates, on average, every 20 seconds, but with substantial variability at the individual subject level (Vanhaudenhuyse et al. 2011). This has been replicated, leading some researchers to argue that the DMN is one of the neural networks whose pattern of connections most strongly varies interindividually, and intraindividually (Finn et al. 2015) under circumstances such as acute stress (Zhang et al. 2019) and when we are engaged in brief activities that require the integration of information (Simony et al. 2016). The DMN, then, is part of our individual neural-signature and, in interaction with attentional networks, arguably constrains processes in a fluctuating rhythm according to past individual experiences and circumstantial tasks. Another important aspect is that the activity of some of its hubs correlates with bodily oscillations such as heartbeats, reflecting the level of selfhood and agency of the experience (Babo-Rebelo, Richter, and Tallon-Baudry 2016).

To connect these findings with Dewey's ideas, I will translate some aspects of his thought into dynamic systems theory, a mathematical framework which has been used to conjoin approaches that describe the evolution of systems over time. According to Dewey, the roots of an aesthetic experience lie in an engagement with the environment enacted through a perceived rhythm characterized by an accumulating tension of doing and undergoing in relationship. I consider that this idea (substituting doing and undergoing in relationship for narrative and attentional processes owing to the fluctuating correlation between DMN and the dorsal attentional network) allows to consider the rhythmic dynamic behind the reflective aspects of experiences driven by the ACE as a case of metastability.

Metastability is a term from dynamic systems theory used in cognitive science to denote a regime of activity predominant in the brain's 'resting state' – i.e., when a subject is not exposed to salient environmental stimuli and cognition is mostly unconstrained and spontaneous – in which “the individual parts of the brain exhibit tendencies to function autonomously at the same time as they exhibit tendencies for coordinated activity” (Fingelkurts and Fingelkurts 2004: 851). According to coordination dynamics, metastability presents slower phases of integration of neural activity – dwells – and fast segregative moments – escapes – in which the global rhythm seems to reshuffle itself. That is not to say that the system fluctuates randomly: the existence of traces of attractors instead of fixed attractors – i.e., a preferred oscillation state – prevents the evolution from being absolutely stochastic, while making it unnecessary for energy to go

⁷It has been argued (Vessel, Starr, and Rubin 2012; Vessel, Starr, and Rubin 2013; Belfi et al. 2019) that the activation of the DMN and some of its dynamics are consistent with reported intense aesthetic experience. However, the fact that these experiments are limited to visual experiences in which images were shown just for a few seconds suggests that we cannot rule out that what these researchers consider to be intense paradigmatic aesthetic experiences are, in fact, sudden intense pleasurable experiences. This seems especially likely if we consider that, during non-explicitly aesthetic auditory comprehension (Simony et al. 2016) and movie watching (Demirtas et al. 2018), tasks that lasted for several minutes, the DMN showed diverse configurations with different functional cognitive consequences.

from one state to another (Tognoli and Kelso 2014). The activity of certain networks is thought to either reduce – e.g., the attentional network – or increase global metastability – e.g. the DMN – (Hellyer et al. 2014), and the anatomical and functional overlapping and connectivity of these networks with aspects of cognition presenting different but intertwined temporalities produces an oscillatory landscape in which metastability is easily lost and slowly regained. In other words, metastability is a fragile rhythmic equilibrium of maximum potentiality in which weak stimuli, such as the consequences of accepting the invitation of an aesthetic affordance, suffice to provoke relevant changes. Environmental engagements sometimes require quick responses, and for this reasons cognitive resources have to be readily at hand; metastability contributes to this responsiveness. Kelso sums up its importance: “[M]etastability guarantees that the living brain [...] never finds itself frozen for any length of time in a particular coordination state: no energy barriers need to be crossed to visit self-organized metastable tendencies. For this reason, it seems likely that natural selection has latched on to this aspect of self-organization, favouring metastability as necessary for adaptive behaviour” (Kelso 2012: 914).

It seems uncontroversial to affirm that aesthetically relevant experiences will develop more easily if there are no previous attractors entraining our cognitive rhythm. That is, these experiences will benefit from a metastable regime. This is also consistent with the mineness of an aesthetic affordance being more easily perceived in the absence of pressing needs constraining our perception. Therefore, a narratively relevant action solicited by an aesthetic affordance would activate some hubs of the DMN, and this network, given the absence of other constraining circumstances, would become the prevalent one. However, since we are within an aesthetic context in which something from the environment draws our attention, the attentional networks will likely regain prevalence after several seconds. Yet, this paying attention to a particular feature will affect the whole experience, and it will lead to the emergence of more salient aspects related to what is now being experienced, soliciting new narrative resources that will have to be integrated into the whole: attentional and narrative activities will shape each other. While this reciprocal influence happens in many experiences, I suggest that the sustained and accumulating nature of the fluctuations between these brain networks is specific to the reflective side of experiences driven by the ACE. More specifically, we experience otherwise unnoticed aspects coming either from the environment or from ourselves, drawing our attention which, in turn, leads to changes in our narrative self in a process in which layers of sense and meaning keep emerging. A rhythm of experience constrained by an underlying cognitive metastable regime characterized by fluid transitions between states dominated by these two networks. The fluctuation in the dominance of the one network or the other will tip the balance toward a bigger influence of narrative or attentional aspects by shaping transient basins of attraction that will affect the trajectory of the system without trapping it. As long as metastability lasts, this ‘enactive attunement’ (Gallagher 2017) between elements that give form to the experience will take place. In other words, we experience aesthetic metastability as an engagement with the environment that generates a unified whole in which everything seems to be narratively relevant and increasingly connected. Yet, metastability is a fragile balance. Increasing attentional activity reduces global metastability and increased synchrony (Hellyer et al. 2014). This circumstance, from an aesthetic point view, is consistent with the fact that it does not matter how deep or moving the experience is, just a touch on our shoulder, an unexpected sound, or one distracting emotion suffices to draw our attention a little bit too much, making metastability disappear and with it our experience.

However, brain networks are not the only oscillation involved in the reflective side of the ACE. In addition to pre-reflective aspects of the ACE, which will be addressed in the next section, brain network dynamics seems to be subject to entrainment from environmental and bodily oscillations (Lakatos, Gross & Thut 2019). The extent of this modulation in an aesthetic context needs to be experimentally evaluated. Yet, in the case of aesthetic metastability, I contend that we experience the agency of the body in the doing and undergoing of our engagement with the environment as a relevant aspect of the overall experience: the movements we produce to keep the rhythm affect how we engage with the music, and a long-held breath will make it seem as though our experience of time has expanded. We become aware of the body as a first prior (Allen and Tsakiris 2019) thanks to its limitations and its capabilities, thanks to the stability it provides and

its deviations from patterns. The body and its oscillations certainly have an effect on the global rhythm. For example, Park et al. (2020) have proved that breathing not only impacts involuntary movements, but also voluntary ones by entraining readiness potential, and Babo-Rebelo, Richter, and Tallon-Baudry (2016) have found a correlation between heartbeats and some hubs of the DMN, shaping the level of selfhood and agency of the experience. That is, bodily rhythms (along with pre-reflective aspects of the ACE, the changing engagement with the environment and other potential aspects) affect the ‘how’ of the experience. All of them contribute to generating and modulating the traces of attractors that softly constrain the transition between different metastable states. In other words, we do not merely experience the evolution of our engagement with the environment: what we experience is the meshing of its mattering to us and us minding about it.

This emphasis on the process rather than the outcome makes explicit aesthetic judgments potential but not necessary outcomes of aesthetic metastability. Certainly, we can force ourselves to focus on an experience because we desperately want to get something out of it, but this emphasis on dissecting what is going on will certainly put the aesthetic component at risk: the attentional overcharge could cause a shrinking of the narrative component, making the experience more analytic than aesthetic. However, beyond the level of conscious monitoring, aesthetic metastability will produce sense and meaning for as long as it lasts by entraining experience to narratively relevant processes that will backstitch the present enactment in previous related ones: we will walk, interact with others, smile, frown, and think about or just feel what we are doing. And while these actions can be relevant in themselves, they will also update our narrative self and add layers to the experience, granting to the one who lives it a feeling that this whole experience is *his*.

To conclude then, the dynamic system enacted by environment, brain, and body at the reflective side of an aesthetically relevant experience may be considered a rhythmic regime of aesthetic metastability in which a variable number of metastable states will reflect changes in the ongoing interaction between narrative and attentional processes without trapping the trajectory of the system. That is, the ‘how’ of the experience constrained by the ongoing aesthetic metastability will be co-determined by aspects of the ‘what’ – the event or object – and the ‘who’ of the experience – the agent – reciprocally attuned by oscillatory activity.

3.3 The asymmetric aesthetic background

In a recent contribution, Despina Stamatopoulou takes into consideration some of Brincker’s ideas on aesthetic experience and expands them by defining its embodied roots. She argues that an aesthetic experience is a “dynamic ‘incubated’ experience (we experience through the background affectivity) which could easily be destabilized and change dynamics if the aesthetic affordances do not support the ‘holding’, or we cannot regulate the negative, or contextual factors intervene. [...] [A] ‘hot cognition’ route rather than a setting of ready-made ‘frozen’ games of make-believe” (Stamatopoulou 2018: 183). As a consequence, “aesthetic experiences can become a field of ‘becoming instead of being’, when the motivational urge to act upon (feeling for the other) gets back to the beholder to be ‘played within’, as potentialities of vicarious I-feelings, while the beholder retains the ‘intersubjective ties’ with the art object (engagement)” (Stamatopoulou 2018: 184). Stamatopoulou contends that the dynamic engagement that scaffolds the unfolding of aesthetic experience is the “emergent background of (a) positive affectivity that derives from sensorimotor and affect synchrony (background emotion/motivational attitude) may be needed/or emerge to hold –stabilize, throughout, the (b) perceptual engagement with the art object/other (the perceiver is receptively ‘attuned to’ the object” (Stamatopoulou 2018: 173). Although most of Stamatopoulou’s ideas resonate with some points already made, I disagree with the importance she assigns to sensorimotor and affect synchrony, and with her idea that what is “critical for aesthetic experiences” is the fact “that we cannot *act upon* while perceptually engaged (the beholder cannot effect changes in the unfolding of the art’s world)” (Stamatopoulou 2018: 171). As in the case of Brincker’s characterization of aesthetic affordance, I believe that the dichotomy these scholars establish between aesthetic and non-aesthetic experiences, by

placing them on different sides of action engagements, does not hold when applied to non-artistic aesthetic experiences or to more dynamic artistic practices: is it impossible to have an aesthetic experience of dancing while dancing? What difference does it make in terms of action possibilities whether a physicist is looking at an equation or at *the* equation that suddenly gives meaning to years of work? From my point of view, sensorimotor aspects play an active role both in pre-reflective and reflective aspects of the experience and, as long as the experience is narratively relevant enough for him, the physicist looking at an equation can have as aesthetic an experience as some people have before a painting in a museum. I also disagree with Stamatopoulou's exclusive focus on positive affectivity. I believe that the cognitive background can grow even in the case of negative affects, should there be higher attentional constraints imposed on the experience by the agent. Certain artworks aim to elicit disgust, repulsion, or a critical view of society. It will be easier if we know this in advance, but, in any case, we can force ourselves to engage with the work and the ensuing experience, however unpleasant it may be, for the sake of its outcome. Getting back to the objective of this section, while I agree with Stamatopoulou about the importance of an affective background, in my opinion its most relevant dynamic attribute is not synchrony, but asymmetry.

In a recent preprint, Gil B. Carvalho and Antonio Damasio propose that the evolutionary persistence and pervasiveness of non-synaptic transmission⁸ (NST) in particular areas of the nervous system, including those linked to information about bodily states such as the limbic system, the brain stem, and parts of the autonomic nervous system, despite its lesser spatiotemporal efficiency, points to an essential role in affectivity: "Whereas movement and perception require precision and gain from speed, the world of affect – moods, and plenty of feelings – can tolerate some vagueness and slowness, perhaps even benefit from them. [...] This would be in keeping with the fact that NST occurs over relatively long timescales – seconds, minutes or even longer –, as opposed to the milli- or even microseconds range involved in synaptic transmission" (Carvalho and Damasio 2019: 16-17). Indeed, it is tempting to link the spatiotemporal dynamics of NST with how particularly salient emotions or moods seem to permeate the whole of cognition, constraining possible actions and their outcomes. NST and the much better-known synaptic transmission should thus be regarded as complementary: synapses predominate in areas that mediate the faster and more precise 'what' of the neural function – e.g., sensory perception, skeletal muscle contraction, higher cognition – whereas NST predominates in regions involved in the slower and less precise 'how' – e.g., affect, arousal (Carvalho and Damasio 2019: 17).

Following this theory, it could be argued that the different but inextricably connected temporal and spatial patterns of affective and other cognitive processes, in the case of sustained activity of both components, lead to an aesthetic asymmetry in which the elements related to environmental engagement – mainly sensorimotor and attentional processes – have faster and more transient consequences, while affective elements need more time to grow but have more pervasive effects. This aesthetic asymmetry generates sensorimotor constraints with narrative relevance if an appropriate integration of affective, bodily, sensorimotor, and other cognitive aspects such as attention takes place. This is the mechanism through which the aesthetic asymmetry affects the pre-reflective side of the ACE; nonetheless, it is also related to the entrainment between brain networks typical of reflective aesthetic metastability. The two processes can coexist and, in that case, influence one another: the metastable states of the reflective side of the rhythm would be nested within the slower and more diffuse activity of the pre-reflective side and the interaction of both parts would contribute to endowing the experience with the temporal depth and cognitive complexity necessary for the emergence of time-extended aesthetic features, such as the dynamic interplay between uncertainty and surprise, responsible for certain pleasurable

⁸Non-synaptic transmission, discovered by Sylvester Vizi in 1969, refers to communication from neurons to neurons or to other cells through different agents – neurotransmitters, neuropeptides, ions or gases – released directly into extracellular space – i.e., not through a synapse – and with the potential, through three-dimensional diffusion, to affect a huge number of non-necessarily close cells. In contrast to synaptic connections, which are one-to-one processes able to convey a precise message from one neuron to another close neuron, non-synaptic transmission is a one-to-many, less precise way for a neuron to modulate the activity of the cells in one particular area.

aspects of aesthetic experiences (Cheung et al. 2019). Yet, the aesthetic asymmetry also plays a role in the emergence of the aesthetic affordance: it primes the mineness through which it invites narratively relevant actions.

Priming is the name given to the psychological phenomenon by which repeated exposure to a given element conditions its subsequent detection. Researchers have theorized the existence of an “affective priming” (Fazio et al. 1986), based on the finding that words with a certain emotional valence cause faster reactions in future interactions with other words presenting a similar valence. Weidler and Abrams (2018) have gone a step further by proving that performing an action as simple as pressing a key speeds up the engagement between related images and words. According to them, their results “imply a more elaborate influence of motor behavior on perception and cognition that has previously been believed. The results also fit well with models of thinking that propose a shared basis for cognition and motor processes (*embodied cognition*)” (1504). Following this cue, I consider that the mineness of the narrative aspects of an aesthetic affordance that emerge on the reflective side of experience is subject to priming by the cognitive background generated on the pre-reflective side, which will thus constrain the affordance and the prospective aesthetic metastability.

Sometimes an aesthetic affordance just strikes us through what seems to be an instantaneous development. On other occasions, the experience takes time: we are drawn to something, we pay attention, and a detail stands out and entrains us to a certain rhythm. In the former situation, it seems that the main factor at play is the sudden enactment of non-primed contents of the narrative self; in the latter, there is more room for processes developing in the background of our experience to play a role by priming the interaction through specific features. However, the problem is that we cannot know how long the priming has been happening. While at work, we may suddenly feel like looking up some information on nearby restaurants, and in perusing some menus we may realize that we are feeling hungry, and thus decide that it is the right moment for a lunch break. Looking for restaurants seemed like a spontaneous decision, but was it really? It might be that some bodily and brain states that correlated with the experience of hunger, subtle enough to remain below conscious awareness, modulated all the behavior just mentioned. It seems uncontroversial to argue that both internal states and previous experiences influence the development of ongoing ones. This is not to say that objects and modes of attention are completely under the control of non-accessible aspects of experience, but rather that there is a continuity between pre-reflective and reflective cognitive aspects of the ACE mediated by dynamic attentional processes integrating brain, body, and environmental inputs. Getting back to Nanay and the discussion about the ACE, we certainly cannot voluntarily force ourselves to reach the attentional threshold where the object appears through its narratively relevant mineness, but there will be circumstances affecting its likeliness; however, since priming arguably takes place beyond our control, it seems far more likely for actions, perceptions or thoughts to be constrained without our noticing it on many more occasions or to a higher degree than we are willing to accept. And for this reason, the cognitive background of aesthetic asymmetry is the backbone of the ACE, the essential element upon which affordances invite us to enact an aesthetic metastability.

We are still left with the question: what triggers this process in the pre-reflective aesthetic background? According to Dewey: “Impulsion designates a movement outward and forward [...] Impulsions are the beginnings of complete experience because they proceed from need; from a hunger and demand that belongs to the organism as a whole and that can be supplied only by instituting definite relations (active relations, interactions) with the environment” (Dewey 1980: 61). An impulsion engenders an experience if it finds resistance: it must surmount obstacles to allow the self to become aware of itself through feeling and interest (Dewey 1980: 62). Dewey situates the origin of this impulsion in the agent; by contrast, I will be more conservative and place the impulsion between agent and environment as the result of an *unrealized* entrainment. There are many examples of unrealized entrainment: our fingers tapping to a beat without our noticing it, the cardiac synchrony recorded in groups attending the same performance (Ardizzi et al. 2020). It has even been demonstrated recently that stimuli below the level of awareness – non-perceived sounds – affect the frequency of voluntary movements (Schurger et al 2017). Unrealized entrainment, however slight, may become aesthetic triggers if they resonate with cognitive aspects able to generate a narratively rooted asymmetry. According to what has been

previously discussed, this unrealized entrainment will be more likely if there are no strong cognitive attractors constraining our experience. That is, the impulsion will benefit from a metastable regime like the one that is characteristic of resting state. Unrealized entrainment will grow in relevance by finding some resistance and overcoming it, that is, if the sensorimotor engagement with the environment keeps feeding this impulsion in relevant ways. If this is so, they will either undergo the dynamic stages previously discussed or, upon encountering too much or too little resistance, they will eventually disappear without crossing the attentional threshold. In the former situation, we may speak of paradigmatic aesthetic experiences; in the latter, of the more common examples of experiences driven by ACE: experiences that affect us without even entering our conscious awareness. An example of this second scenario might be: it is a spring afternoon and we are working at our desk when the sunlight enters the window; we feel like changing the music playlist we have been listening to for another one with songs we were listening to last summer; on doing this, we feel a slight wave of heat rushing through our body and continue working. This shows an environmental element – sunlight – that, when perceived, triggers a narratively relevant small impulsion – e.g., being at the beach, being on holiday, not being at work – that affects us – e.g., lack of concentration, memories from the past, anticipation of the summer to come. Its persistence will generate a rhythmic asymmetry that, in virtue of the emerging constraints, results in a meaningful action: listening to music that soothes our desire to be in the beach. The impulse is fulfilled, the resistance disappears, and an aesthetic outcome – enjoying the music – permeates the whole experience. Certainly, this experience might enter our reflective side and bring about an actual evocation of summer days within us, and hence the conscious decision to listen to music consistent with this memory. The reaching of reflective awareness definitely marks a qualitative difference, but it is not essential.

In order to discuss how different sides of the ACE interact in a much more paradigmatic scenario, I will resort to an example used by Nanay to present his theory of aesthetic attention: the way some of Abbas Kiarostami's films end. He contends: "The last five minutes of these films work more like an avant-garde film, avoiding any identification. But precisely because this is only the five minutes of the film, which follows ninety or so minutes of intense identification and non-distributed attention, the aesthetic experience that follows is all the more intense" (Nanay 2016: 181). Instead, I would argue that the predominant moments of intense identification scaffold a narratively relevant engagement that makes us care about the protagonists' fate. If at a certain point in a film we accept the invitation of the aesthetic affordances, that is, if we start to engage with them through the mineness of the offering and they successfully solicit reflective narrative resources, this engagement will not suddenly disappear without a trace in the last five minutes: we will be so invested in the narration that the lingering and ongoing effects of aesthetic metastability will keep constraining these very detached parts, attuned to the new situation, with narrative relevance, and these will be perceived as meaningful. And this is something that cannot occur if the initial parts were missing. The shift in the narrative tone can certainly be felt as a surprise, and draw our attention in a different way, but an extended activation of the aesthetic background helps to bind the experience. It could be said that most films narratively prime the experience of their closing minutes, thereby ensuring that we are in the right state to fully engage with the final acts.

4 Concluding remarks and open questions

Inspired by John Dewey's conceptualization of rhythm in experience, I have presented a theoretical model of the cognitive dynamics behind aesthetically relevant experiences. It integrates different rhythmic processes that arguably underlie pre-reflective and reflective sides of experience within the unified framework of a continuous aesthetic component of experience that relates everyday events and paradigmatic aesthetic experiences. I did not intend to present an exhaustive list of elements that play a role in the ACE; rather, I have offered some dynamically relevant nodes that I consider able to shunt general experience toward the aesthetic. Each individual aspect is backed by empirical results; yet, the

interactions, their consequences, and the general idea of aesthetic continuity behind this model is absolutely open to future research.

The different dynamic processes identified in this model are considered as some raw elements necessary for holding together aesthetic interactions between agent and environment. The initial unrealized entrainment is the most common start of the enactment of the ACE. It may trigger an asymmetric aesthetic background in which affectively mediated narrative resources closely follow upon the faster sensorimotor attentional aspects. This asymmetry entrains experience and actions that can be felt to be meaningful enough to sooth the impulsion. However, if there is sustained narrative priming, the attentional threshold may be reached. At this point, an aesthetic affordance, inviting more narrative resources thanks to the mineness of its solicitation, opens the door to the reflective side of experience. The differential fluctuation of brain networks, the evolution of environmental circumstances, and the oscillations of the body will contribute to the enactment of a regime of aesthetic metastability with an evolving number of potential states. Aesthetic metastability will be experienced as an effortless flow in which actions, feelings, thoughts, and perceptions seem to be narratively relevant and increasingly connected. Metastability is thus one element that brings continuity to the aesthetic component of experience: it is a dynamic feature from which the aesthetic usually arises, weakened as attention grows, and reinforced again as hubs of the DMN become active at the reflective side. Metastability grants to certain aesthetically relevant experiences their unity and coherence. However, where Dewey speaks of the aesthetic in experience as a rhythmic form of doing and undergoing in relationship, I contend that the cognitive rhythm that constrains its temporal evolution is mainly an evolving entrainment between narrative and attentional processes. These two cognitive aspects interact through different dynamics both at the pre-reflective and the reflective side of the ACE and affect experience quite differently. They are two relevant cognitive actors of aesthetic engagements.

Beyond Dewey's capital influence, my model is also inspired, among others, by the work of Marie Brincker and Bence Nanay. More specifically, by Brincker's notion of aesthetic affordance and Nanay's analysis on the role of attention in aesthetic experiences. Yet, I have tried to integrate some of their ideas within the framework of an enactive aesthetic component of experience connecting pre-reflective and reflective sides of experience, as an attempt to comply with what Dewey considered aesthetics' primary task: restore the continuity between intensified forms of experience and everyday events. Certainly, there are still plenty of open questions about this aesthetic rhythm: Which are the differences between performer and observer in aesthetically relevant events? How do interindividual and intraindividual differences in DMN activation condition aesthetic engagements? How do sharing an aesthetically relevant experience shapes the experience?

In essence, this is an aesthetics paper, but it can be also regarded as a discussion on the cognitive dynamics behind a particular type of interaction between agent and environment. Specifically, I consider that the notion of rhythm as an emerging unified constraint enacted by the entrainment of different oscillators can contribute to the debate between enactivism and ecological psychology on the dynamics of cognition. Raja (2018, 2019, 2020) has provided an ecological framework of resonance as a material process through which the activity of the CNS resonates with the organized activity of the agent within her environment. More specifically, he characterizes resonance as "the process by which the dynamics at the scale of the neural system are constrained by the same informational variable that constrains the dynamics at the scale of behaviour" (2020: 20). Nonetheless, according to Ryan and Gallagher (in press), ecological theories such as Raja's have problems accounting for how humans and other organisms can be active forces that shape their environment. While I agree with their analysis of the limitations of ecological resonance, I do not think that the concept of attunement – proposed by Ryan and Gallagher as an addition or possible replacement to resonance – is sufficient to serve as a foundation for non-representational embodied cognition either. We certainly attune to and are attuned by events and objects from the environment; social cognition can be considered as a process of attunement. But in the same way that resonance focuses on variables present both at the ecological and the intra-organismic scale, attunement focuses on processes of progressive enactment of shared constraints, which, I consider, leaves unaddressed the issue of the integration

of these dynamics within a narratively relevant scale. In other words, how do resonating with the environment and attuning to others' actions become part of our lived present and then part of our narrative self? The present paper has tried to address this issue in the specific case of aesthetically relevant experiences by resorting to a notion of rhythm as open entrainment based on Dewey. I hope I have shown that rhythm can be useful for enactive aesthetics but also for future work aimed at developing an account of non-representational embodied cognition together with ecological resonance and enactive attunement.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

- Allen, M., Tsakiris, M. (2019). The body as first prior: Interoceptive predictive processing and the primacy of self-model. In Tsakiris, M., De Preester, H. (Eds.), *The Interoceptive Mind: From homeostasis to awareness* (pp. 27-45). Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- Ardizzi, M. et al. (2020). Audience spontaneous entrainment during the collective enjoyment of live performances: physiological and behavioral measurements. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-60832-7>
- Author (2020). Rhythm ‘n’ Dewey: an adverbialist ontology of art. *Rivista di Estetica* 73(1), 79-95.
- Azzalini, D., Rebollo, I., Tallon-Baudry, C. (2019). Visceral signals shape brain dynamics and cognition. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* 2(6), 488-509.
- Babo-Rebelo, M., Richter, C. G., Tallon-Baudry, C. (2016). Neural Responses to Heartbeats in the Default Network Encode the Self in Spontaneous Thoughts. *Journal of Neuroscience* 36 (30), 7829-7840.
- Belfi, A. M. et al. (2019). Dynamics of aesthetic experience are reflected in the default-mode network. *Neuroimage*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2018.12.017>.
- Brincker, M. (2015). The Aesthetic Stance – On the Conditions and Consequences of Becoming a Beholder. In Scarinzi, A. (Ed.), *Aesthetics and the Embodied Mind: Beyond Art Theory and The Cartesian Mind-Body Dichotomy* (pp. 117-138). New York, Springer.
- Bruineberg, J., Rietveld, E. (2014). Self-organization, free energy minimization, and optimal grip on a field of affordances. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2014.00599>
- Carroll, N. (2012). Recent Approaches to Aesthetic Experience. *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism* 70(2), 165-177.
- Carvalho, G., Damasio, A (2019). Non-Synaptic Transmission and the Foundations of Affect. *Preprint*. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints201901.0252.v1>
- Cheung, V. K. M. et al. (2019). Uncertainty and Surprise Jointly Predict Musical Pleasure and Amygdala, Hippocampus, and Auditory Cortex Activity. *Current Biology* 29(23), 4084-4092.
- Colombetti, G. (2013). *The Feeling Body: Affective Science Meets the Enactive Mind*. Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Demirtas, M. et al. (2018). Distinct modes of functional connectivity induced by movie-watching. *NeuroImage*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2018.09.042>
- Dewey, J. (1980). *Art as Experience*. New York: Penguin Group.
- Dings, R. (2018). Understanding phenomenological differences in how affordances solicit action. An exploration. *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Science* 17(4), 681-699.
- Dings, R. (2019). The dynamic and recursive interplay of embodiment and narrative identity. *Philosophical Psychology* 32(2), 186-210.
- Dreon, R. (2019). Framing cognition. Dewey’s potential contributions to some enactivist issues. *Synthese*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-019-02212-x>.
- Fazio, R. H. et al. (1986). On the automatic activation of attitudes. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 50, 229-238.
- Fingelkurts, A. N. A., Fingelkurts, A. L. A. (2004). Making complexity simpler: multivariability and metastability in the brain. *International Journal of Neuroscience* 114(7), 843-862.
- Finn, E. S. et al. (2015). Functional connectome fingerprinting: identifying individuals using patterns of brain connectivity. *Nature Neuroscience* 18, 1664-1671.
- Forlè, F. (2018). The ‘How’ and ‘What’ of Aesthetic Experience. Some Reflections Based on Nöe’s *Strange Tools*. *Art and Human Nature. Phenomenology and Mind* 14, 18-28.
- Fox, M. D. et al. (2005). The human brain is intrinsically organized into dynamic, anticorrelated functional networks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 102(27), 9673-9678.
- Fries, P. (2015). Rhythms for cognition: Communication through coherence. *Neuron* 88(7), 220-235.
- Gallagher, S. (2011). Aesthetics and kinaesthetics. In Krois, J. M. (Ed.), *Sehen und Handeln* (pp. 99-113). Weinheim, John Wiley and Sons.
- Gallagher, S. (2017). *Enactivist Interventions: Rethinking the Mind*. Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- Gallagher, S. (2019). Precis: Enactivist Interventions. *Philosophical Studies* 176: 803-806
- Goldman, A. H. (2013). The Broad View of Aesthetic Experience. *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism* 71(4), 323-333.
- Hellyer, P. J. (2014). The control of global brain dynamics: opposing actions of frontoparietal control and default mode networks of attention. *Journal of Neuroscience* 34(2), 451-461.
- Hoeg, J., Alba, J. W., Dahl, D. W. (2010). The good, the bad, and the ugly: Influence of aesthetics on product feature judgments. *Journal of Consumer Psychology* 20(4), 419-430.
- Hutto, D. (2015). Enactive aesthetics: Philosophical reflections on artful minds. In Scarinzi, A. (Ed.), *Aesthetics and the Embodied Mind: Beyond Art Theory and the Cartesian Mind-Body Dichotomy* (pp. 211-227). New York, Springer.
- James, W. (1983). *Essays in Psychology*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Johnson, M. (2017). *Embodied Mind, Meaning and Reason. How our Bodies Give Rise to Understanding*. Chicago, The University of Chicago Press.
- Juarrero, A. (2015). What does the closure of context-sensitive constraints mean for determinism, autonomy, self-determination, and agency? *Progress in Biophysics and Molecular Biology* 119, 510-521.

- Kelso, J. A. S. (1995). *Dynamic patterns: the self-organization of brain and behavior*. Cambridge, MIT Press.
- Kelso, J. A. S. (2012). Multistability and metastability: Understanding dynamic coordination in the brain. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B Biological Sciences* 367(1591), 906-918.
- Kelso, J. A. S., Tognoli, E. (2007). Toward a complementary neuroscience: Metastable coordination dynamics of the brain. In Perlovsky, L. I., Kozma, R. (Eds.), *Neurodynamics of cognition and consciousness* (pp. 39-59). Berlin: Springer.
- Klimesch, W. (2018). The frequency architecture of brain and body oscillations: an analysis. *European Journal of Neuroscience* 48, 2431-2453.
- Klofstad, C. A., Anderson, R. C., Nowicki, S. (2015). Perceptions of Competence, Strength, and Age Influence Voters to Select Leaders with Lower-Pitched Voices. *PLoS ONE* 10(8): e0133779.
- Krampe, M. (1991). Environmental meaning. In Zube, E. H., Moore, G. T. (Eds.), *Advances in environment, behavior, and design* (vol. 3, pp. 231-267). New York, Plenum.
- Kuciy, A. et al. (2020). Electrophysiological dynamics of antagonistic brain networks reflect attentional fluctuations. *Nature Communications*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-14166-2>
- Lakatos, P., Gross, J., Thut, G. (2019). A New Unifying Account of the Roles of Neuronal Entrainment. *Current Biology* 29, 890-905.
- Mather, M., Thayer, J. (2018). How heart rate variability affects emotion regulation brain networks. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences* 19: 98-104.
- Mumcu, Y., Kimzan, H. S. (2015). The Effect of Visual Product Aesthetics on Consumers' Price Sensitivity. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 26: 528-534.
- Najafi, M. et al. (2016). Overlapping communities reveal rich structure in large-scale brain networks during rest and task conditions. *Neuroimage* 15(135), 92-106.
- Nanay, B. (2016). *Aesthetics as Philosophy of Perception*. Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- Nanay, B. (2019). *Aesthetics: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- Nöe, A. (2016). *Strange Tools: Art and Human Nature*. New York, Hill and Wang.
- Park, H. et al (2020). Breathing is coupled with voluntary action and the cortical readiness potential. *Nature Communications*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-13967-9>
- Pessoa, L. (2017). A Network Model of the Emotional Brain. *Trends in Cognitive Science* 21(5), 357-371.
- Pikovsky, A., Rosenblum, M., Kurths, J. (2001). *Synchronization: A Universal Concept in Nonlinear Sciences*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Raja, V. (2018). A theory of resonance: towards an ecological cognitive architecture. *Minds Machines* 28, 29-51.
- Raja, V. (2019). From metaphor to theory: the role of resonance in perceptual learning. *Adaptive Behavior* 27, 405-421.
- Raja, V. (2020). Resonance and radical embodiment. *Synthese*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-020-02610-6>.
- Raichle, M. E. (2015). The brain's default mode network. *Annuals Reviews of Neuroscience* 38, 433-447.
- Ramstead, M. J. D. et al. (2016). Cultural Affordances: Scaffolding Local Worlds Through Shared Intentionality and Regimes of Attention. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01090>
- Rietveld, E., Kiverstein, J. (2014). A Rich Landscape of Affordances. *Ecological Psychology* 26(4), 325-352.
- Roberts, J. A. et al. (2019). Metastable brain waves. *Nature Communications*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08999-0>.
- Ryan, K., Gallagher, S. (in press). Between Ecological Psychology and Enactivism: Is There Resonance? *Frontiers in Psychology*.
- Simony, E. et al. (2016). Dynamic reconfiguration of the default mode network during narrative comprehension. *Nature Communication*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms12141>.
- Schurger, A. et al. (2017). Entrainment of Voluntary Movement to Undetected Auditory Regularities. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-15126-w>
- Skov, M., Nadal, M. (2020). Farewell to Art: Aesthetics as a Topic in Psychology and Neuroscience. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691619897963>.
- Slors, M., Jongepier, F. (2014). Mineness without Minimal Selves. *Journal of Consciousness Studies* 21(7), 193-219.
- Smith, V., Mitchell, D. J., Duncan, J. (2018). Role of the Default Mode Network in Cognitive Transitions. *Cerebral Cortex*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhy167>.
- Stamatopoulou, D. (2018). Empathy and the aesthetic: Why does art still move us? *Cognitive Processing* 19, 169-186.
- Tognoli, E., Kelso, J. A. (2014). The metastable brain. *Neuron* 81(1), 35-48.
- Trost, W., Vuilleumier, P. (2013). Rhythmic entrainment as a mechanism for emotion induction by music. In Cochrane, T., Fantino, B., Scherer, K. R. (Eds.), *The Emotional Power of Music: Multidisciplinary perspectives on musical arousal, expression and social control* (pp. 213-227). Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- Trost, W., Labbé, C., Grandjean, D. (2017). Rhythmic entrainment as a musical affect induction mechanism. *Neuropsychologia* 96, 96-110.
- Vanhaudenhuyse, A. et al. (2011). Two Distinct Neuronal Networks Mediate the Awareness of Environment and of Self. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience* 23(3), 570-578.
- Varela, F. J. (1999). The specious present: A neurophenomenology of time consciousness. In Petitot, J. et al. (Eds.), *Writing Science. Naturalizing phenomenology: Issues in contemporary phenomenology and cognitive science* (pp. 266-314). Redwood City, Stanford University Press.
- Vessel, E., Starr, G., Rubin, N. (2012). The Brain on Art: Intense Aesthetic Experience Activates the Default Mode Network. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2012.00066>.

Weidler, B. J., Abrams, R. A. (2018). Simple actions activate semantic associations. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review* 25, 1500-1506.

Withagen, R. et al. (2012). Affordances can invite behavior: Reconsidering the relationship between affordances and agency. *New Ideas in Psychology* 30(2), 250-258.

Zelano, C. et al. (2016). Nasal respiration entrains human limbic oscillations and modulates cognitive function. *Journal of Neurosciences* 36, 12448-12467.

Zhang, W. et al. (2019) Acute stress alters the 'default' brain processing. *NeuroImage*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2019.01.063>